

Role of Capacity Building on Economic Development of Women in Mogadishu Somalia

Mohamud Dahir Hilif^{1,2}

¹ Faculty of Economics and Management, Somali International University, Mogadishu, Somalia

² Senior Child Protection Officer, Ministry of Justice and Constitutional Affairs, Somalia

Abstract: The capacity building of women is crucial for its significant contribution to society and sustainable economic development in Somalia. These institutions prioritize not only their business interests but also their socio-economic development objectives. The capacity building play role reducing poverty by increasing employment and income, thereby enhancing women's capacity for sustainable development and eco-comic growth. This research aims to examine the influence of capacity building on economic development of women in Somalia. The study utilized a correlational research design to investigate the relationship between capacity building provision and women's economic advancement. The data was analyzed using SPSS software after being collected from 135 responded. The study found a significant positive correlation between capacity building services and women's economic development. The study indicates that capacity building and overall economic progress significantly enhance the economic progress of women in Somalia. The research findings suggest that a higher degree of adoption of capacity building has the potential to enhance women's financial status, self-assurance, and improve their chances for uplifting themselves from poverty. These outcomes can significantly contribute to the overall progress and well-being of society as a whole.

Keywords: Capacity Building, Women Empowerment, Economic Development, Poverty, Mogadishu-Somalia.

I. Introduction

The concept of capacity building means all efforts geared towards the development of human skills, intellectual capabilities, and talents for a meaningful and satisfied life in societies and communities (Ihekweba Hope et al., 2022). However, capacity building, as the development of knowledge, skills, and approaches by individuals and groups of people relevant to sustainable development, thus focuses attention on the creation of an ongoing quality of life society through an increase in real per-capital income development in women empowerment and participation in highly level economic development. Of the country (Ihekweba Hope et al., 2022). Capacity building refers to promoting women's economic growth by providing abilities that directly affect women entrepreneurs' development and produce high quality (UNICEF, 2020). Another way to build capacity is by giving power to a woman and having direct life regarding desired social advantage, political and economic goals, or economic sustainability (Al-Shami et al., 2021). Women's capacity building for economic development plays a crucial role in promoting female ideas to create income and sustainable economic development in more countries (Al-Shami et al., 2021). Meanwhile, empowerment is a process by which women increase their own productivity, alleviate poverty, and participate in economic development (Sharma, A., et al., 2012). However, women have become major players in the economy of a country today. and they have direct, positive, and strong relationships. Participation in economic activities varies with each socio-cultural situation and economic growth (Handaragama et al., 2013).

On the other hand, women's capacity building is a powerful tool in society development, economic growth, and self-employment opportunities for the unemployed, exclusively women, to improve their lifestyle, particularly in developing countries (Hilif et al., 2023) Women's empowerment is a multidimensional community process to help individuals gain control over factors that affect their lives and support economic empowerment by generating employment, income, and providing entrepreneurial opportunities. (Seyfi et al., 2023) Additionally, female empowerment programs encourage and establish sources of income and accumulate capital (Afrin et al., 2010).

Entrepreneurship models play a crucial role in helping women entrepreneurs develop their SME (Rasnayake et al., 2013). A woman entrepreneur is a self-confident, innovative, and creative woman proficient in achieving economic independence alone, as an individual, or in collaboration or alliance, and generates employment opportunities for others through starting, establishing, and running an initiative while keeping pace with her private, family, and social life (Sharma, A., et al., 2012).

Capacity-building training plays a vital role in assisting women in classifying their own challenges, starting change, and understanding how training affects women's economic activities. (Collett et al., 2009). On the other hand, capacity-building programs in business programs create self-esteem and residence opportunities for society, develop economic activities, improve household income and social welfare, participate in poverty eradication and reduction, and achieve economic development goals, enhancing the sustainability of the community's maintenance and livelihood (Ge et al., 2022). Furthermore, these tools are crucial for promoting women in society and expanding economics in developing countries (Sajuyigbe et al., 2017).

On the other hand, women's capacity-building It has a significant effect on the income of the household and improves economic activities, family income, and social welfare (Ge et al., 2022). Meanwhile, capacity building through training is important, according to women's empowerment, to achieve economic development objectives and self-reliance (Pollyn et al., 2016). More skills are essential for productivity, increasing the ability to deal with change disasters, and facilitating the diversification of maintenance (Collett et al., 2009). Women's business is creating positive effects and contributing to economic development and efficiency in household income (Razavi S., 2012).

Human development and human welfare in women's economic development are creating opportunities, raising the standard of living and participating in economic activities, human development, poverty reduction, and the achievement of the Millennium Development Goals (Usman, A. et al., 2016). According to developing countries, women are contributors to the economic support of their households (Mehra et al., 1997). in Africa It is estimated that 96 percent of rural women engage in farm work, and 40 percent of small farms are managed by both cash and substance income to support their lives (Mehra et al., 1997). The primary objectives of women in rural Africa believe that rural governments offer them no real hope for change and empowerment in relationships of society power relatives. This could also be seen form is significant evidence that rural women are generally neglected, and consistently have lost in this process (Kongolo, et al., 2002). Furthermore, the relationship between women empowerment and economic development is very crucial which are reducing poverty, increasing opportunity, economic growth and pro-poor development of any strategy rising economy (Hjelmström et al., 2017).

II. Literature Review

2.1 Capacity building: Basic Concepts

Capacity can be defined as a person's ability to do something in order to achieve the goal; it is the ability to carry out its intended purpose of community (Mahmud, et al., 2016). Meanwhile concept of women capacity building is the process of enhancing the ability of women in organizations and societies perform appropriate functions effectively and achieve intended goals (World Health Organization, et al., 2001). Capacity building concept is very crucial (Khan, et al., 1998) in all sectors, and it was used as tool for improving the abilities to perform fundamental activities and to achieve and maintain of long-term sustainable growth with the aim of enhancing the quality of life for individuals (Ibrahim et al., 2010). Capacity building aims enhancing socio economic development; therefore, all capacity programs should be targeted at the different levels and dimensions of the communities (de Rooij et al., 2005), including women's empowerment.

The capacity building initiatives play crucial role in increasing and strengthening knowledge, skills, abilities, attitude change, through e.g. training, awareness raising, etc. and providing the conditions for their implementation, which ultimately increase of self-esteem of women (de Rooij, et al., 2005). Thus, empowering women economically, socially, and politically has significant role in community development (Mahmud, et al., 2016). This shows that capacity building programs not only effect women but also contributes to community development at large. Furthermore, capacity building of women has connections with entrepreneurship which focusses on equipping people with power and skills that help them utilize their talents and capabilities (Mahmud, et al., 2016).

2.2 Capacity building of Women: Goals and Importance

Role of Capacity Building on Economic Development of Women in Mogadishu Somalia

The primary objective of capacity building for women is to enable them to reach their full potential and participate equally in society. In its broad sense, these objectives encompass economic empowerment, social and political participation, skill and knowledge enhancement, and decision-making enhancement (Jabeen, et., al., 2010). Some initiatives focus on equipping women with the skills and knowledge they need to be financially independent, while others could involve training in business management, financial literacy, or vocational skills. (Chen, et., al., 2002). All programs enhance women's capacity in leadership, public speaking, advocacy, computer literacy to legal rights awareness, which eventually contributes building women's confidence and self-belief so they can make informed choices about their lives. (Heywood, et., al., 2020).

Schlurmann, et., al. (2011) argue that capacity building of women plays crucial role in promoting economic progress of women and help them achieve sustainable their quality of life. Generally, economic development approach of capacity building initiatives is long-term process designed to enhance human lives (Gumbo, et., al., 2005). Therefore, empowerment is vital for women to gain strength and self-confidence to get change as well as to be responsive towards change for better current and future living (Gumbo, et., al., 2005).

Women, as part of the society, usually play essential role in local, national and international economic development, generate employment and support social progress. These issues are clear in poor communities as women create opportunities for the future of the societies (Dibie, et., al., 2015). Capacity building positively impacts women-owned small enterprises, contributing to developing economies and driving positive, productive growth in all nations (Dibie, et., al., 2015). Studies indicate that capacity building through advocacy and business practices is crucial for empowering individuals to achieve sustainable goals (Eger, et., al., 2018). Capacity building positively impacts productivity and sustainable economic expansion, with key elements including training, equipping, and mentoring. The concept of capacity building has several practices and applications, however, strengthening individual, organizational, and environmental capacities lay the groundwork for meaningful participation in national and local development processes, promoting sustainable development outcomes (Vincent, et., al., 2015).

Capacity building involves courage, women's skills development, and economic growth, which directly impact households' income by creating opportunities and allowing them to control their own economic expansion (Duflo, et., al., 2012). Empowering women plays a crucial role in society, contributing to poverty alleviation, sustainable economic development, and improving their livelihoods, ensuring self-reliance and efficient self-employment (Duflo, et., al., 2012). It is clear that capacity building significantly impacts women's socio-economic status by creating opportunities in a dynamic economic culture, thereby enhancing their participation in social developments (Shafique, et., al., 2020). Ideally, economic empowerment increases women's access to economic resources and participate opportunities including jobs, financial services, property and other productive assets, skills development and market information. This will boost the opportunity for women in business environment to engage in small enterprises business, and generate income for self-employment (Shafique, et., al., 2020).

Furthermore, women's economic capacity building is crucial for sustainable small business development and poverty reduction, and they significantly contribute to Somalia's economy, particularly in micro and small business sectors (Shafique, et., al., 2020; Tsafack, et., al., 2011). In short, women capacity building is a strategy for workforce expansion, promoting societal and community support for women's contributions to prosperity, economic value creation, and maintaining standard living (Shafique, et., al., 2020). Practically, these programs enhance not only individual capacities but also institutional capacity by combining comprehensive economic development schedules and organizational objectives, thereby achieving essential goals through a comprehensive approach (Humphries, et., al., 2011).

2.3 Economic Development of Women

Economic development is crucial for community growth, employment, poverty reduction, and sustainable development by integrating economic and environmental aspects (Panth, et., al., 2021). However, the economic development of women aims to ensure full or more productive employment to achieve their social and economic goals (Abd Hakim, et., al., 2022). Economic development improves education, well-being, income, living standards, social development, provides business opportunities, and helps individuals face challenges in local, national, and global life by enhancing overall living standards (Oshikoya, et., al., 1998). However economic development promotes or help lift people and increase essential investment, get more production and reduce the poverty by creating jobs, improving income levels, and enhancing their living standards. (Ali, et., al., 2016). Promoting women and small medium enterprises in developing countries significantly contributes to economic progress and industrial development, encouraging women to participate

in social development and create employment opportunities (Aris, 2007). Additionally, women's capacity building significantly impacts small and medium enterprises in Somalia, promoting socioeconomic development, household fund generation, and self-reliance within their community (Guled, et. al., 2017). Economic development of women is crucial for socio-economic growth, providing access to resources, opportunities, jobs, financial services, self-reliance, and reducing family income dependency (Morrison, et. al., 2004).

Therefore, women should improve their entrepreneurial capabilities as entrepreneurship fosters creativity and innovation, promoting women's involvement in development-oriented policies that promote productive activities, poverty eradication, and sustainable economic growth (Bertaux, et. al., 2007). Women empowerment is crucial for achieving their economic growth and contribute to their families, societies, national economies, and fight against poverty (Sohail, (2014). Therefore, in order to enhance level of women empowerment, there must be includes women awareness of their rights, self-confidence, to have a control over their lives and their ability to bring a change in the society (Sohail, 2014). Women empowerment is generally improving and encourage women to become independent and participate in all aspects of society, and realizing they can make a significant contribution to society. (Ashraf, et. al., 2018). In this era, women empowerment on economic development plays a very important role in enhancing the confidence of women participating in economic development in our society, according to various studies. (Jahan, et. al., 2015).

III. Related Previous Studies

Ihekwa& Cynthia (2022) examined role of women capacity building in sustainable development in Nigeria, and identified low self-esteem, illiteracy, child-marriage, family challenges, corruption, and poor program implementation as significant obstacles to women capacity building in Nigeria. Therefore, the paper suggests, among other things, that the government increase the number of skills acquisition centers for women and appoint persons with proven record of integrity to manage these facilities. The authors argued that most women's capacitybuilding programs are managed by corrupt government officials who often divert funds to their personal accounts. Khan (2015) explored gender equality issues, particularly women's empowerment and entrepreneurship, in his study on capacity development and gender equality. The author argues that gender inequality hinders economic growth and development, thereby empowering women and causing them to remain powerless and backward. The author also added that women have limited economic assets, limited consumption entitlements, limited access to economic opportunities, and a significant social and political gap. The paper that gender equality can be significantly addressed through thoughtful policy regimes that promote women's empowerment and entrepreneurship.

Pollyn (2016) studied the impact of capacity building initiatives on Nigeria's sustainable development agenda, analyzing its pros and cons, cost and benefit, success and failure of past and present programs, and necessary policy directives. The paper advocates for corruption-free human capacity building and development schemes in Nigeria to achieve sustainable development goals through efficient management. To implement effective human capacity building and development initiatives, human capacity development initiatives should focus on youth, with special empowerment for development agencies and youth vocational training centers across the country, and shift from certificate acquisition and white-collar job training to knowledge economy-based schemes. With this regard, central government agencies should monitor bilateral development agency funds and local capacity building agencies and NGOs for effective utilization and result-oriented schemes. In summary, education is crucial for capacity building and development, as educated individuals are more productive and can drive economic growth and improve welfare.

Kulmie, et. al. (2023) conducted a study on the role of entrepreneurship training on job creation and youth empowerment, and stated that entrepreneurship training as capacity development tool is a strategic approach to youth empowerment including women and young girls, fostering entrepreneurial spirit, innovation, and growth. The authors emphasize that training significantly contributes to the creation of employment opportunities and the empowerment of youth. Therefore, the study suggests that enhancing entrepreneurial education programs to help young people overcome socioeconomic challenges and create jobs. It recommends providing comprehensive training for youth, especially in developing nations. Governments should develop policies promoting entrepreneurship as a tool for youth empowerment, integrate these with national initiatives, and prioritize workforce enhancements. Furthermore, universities and educational and training institutions should implement entrepreneurship-focused training programs to enhance young individuals' employability by equipping them with market-relevant skills. Batool, et.al. (2021) assessed role of women empowerment on economic development, stability and self-reliance, stating that women cannot play an

important role in economic development unless they are educated and empowered with right skills. Women empowerment is a continuous process that can be achieved through women's development programs

Doepke & Tertilt (2019) argued that women empowerment decreases inequality between men and women, adding that women empowerment is crucial in developing countries, leading to reduced poverty levels and improved economic growth. Economic development and women empowerment are closely related, as empowerment initiatives safeguard women's participation in the country's economic development. Experts contend that women involvement in reducing poverty is required. Put it simply, women empowerment involves empowering women to understand their rights, build self-confidence, and take control of their lives, both at home and outside, while also influencing societal change. Muthoni (2013) studied the influence of training on the performance and growth of women-owned small enterprises business (SMES), stating that women are playing a crucial role in the socio-economic development in developing economies, as their business significantly contributes to poverty alleviation in developing countries. Riaz and Chaudhry (2021) study found that women's empowerment, education, skills development, participation in SMEs, and economic, and social empowerment significantly influence poverty, with household size and family setup also positively influencing it. However, women's empowerment is utilized to acknowledge the challenges faced by women who are impoverished and poverty-stricken (Sule Magaji & Ahmad, 2024)

IV. Methodology

The study aimed to investigate role of capacity building on economic development of women in Mogadishu, Somalia, specifically at Salaam Somali Bank, using correlational research design. This research design allows to investigate the relationships between variables without the researcher manipulating or controlling any of them. Correlational research design helps understand how things are connected in the real world. The population of this study is the staff of Slam Somali Bank in Mogadishu Somalia. A sample of 152 individuals was selected from a 250-participant population, with only 135 respondents available for data collection, resulting in an 88% response rate, using purposive and simple random sampling techniques. The study utilized self-administered questionnaires, and the results were presented using frequency tables and percentages. Miller (1983) suggests that this tool is the most cost-effective method for gathering primary data from a large number of respondents. The data were analyzed by using SPSS. The research findings, based on analyzed responses, provided insights into the role capacity building on economic development of women in Mogadishu, Somalia.

V. Results and Discussion

5.1 Demographic Information

According to the results in Table 1, men made up most respondents (79.26%), with women making up 20.74% of the total. This gender gap is attributed to a number of things, including cultural beliefs and social norms. The table 1 also reveals that respondents who were 31-45 years old (61.48%) made up the majority, while respondents who were 18 to 30 years old (31.11%) came in second. A total of 7.41% of respondents were above the 46 and above. According to the results of the educational level education, 25.93% of the participants had Diploma, 44.44% had Bachelor, 11.11% had Masters, 18.52% had others. Table 1 demonstrates that the participants in this study possessed a satisfactory level of literacy and exhibited heightened competence in comprehending and assessing the various components of the questionnaire (Blair, 2013; Martin, 2006; Uma, 2000).

Table 1: Demographic information

Category	Frequency	Valid percent
Gender		
Female	28	20.74
Male	107	79.26
Total	135	100
Age		
18-30	42	31.11
31-45	83	61.48
46 above	10	7.41
Total	135	100
Educational level		
Diploma	35	25.93
Bachelor	60	44.44

Masters	15	11.11
Others	25	18.52
Total	135	100

Role of capacity building on economic development of women in Somalia

The primary objective of this study was to analyze the role of capacity building on economic development of women in Mogadishu, Somalia. The results demonstrate a significant correlation between capacity building and the economic development of women ($r = 0.787$, $p < 0.00$), indicating that capacity building has a statistically positive effect on enhancing the economic development of women, as evident from Table 2. These findings are supported by most respondents who expressed agreement with the notion that capacity building can contribute to economic advancement of women. Consequently, the implementation of capacity building programs is expected to further boost the economic development of women.

Table 2: Correlations between Capacity Building on Economic Development of Women in Mogadishu- Somalia.

		Capacity Building	Economic Development of Women
Capacity Building	Pearson Correlation	1	.787**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	135	135
Economic Development of Women	Pearson Correlation	.787**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	135	135

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Moreover, the results presented in table 3 reveals that the capacity building beta rating stands at 0.787. The results indicate that a rise of 100 percent in capacity building is expected to result in a corresponding increase of 78.7 percent in economic development of women. It should be noted that capacity building programs are essential for reducing gender inequality that hinders their economic growth and development, thereby empowering women and causing them to remain powerless and backward.

Table 3, Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients		
1	(Constant)	1.886	.110		17.125	.000
	Capacity Building	.521	.035	.787	14.722	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Economic Development of Women in Mogadishu Somalia

The findings presented in table 3 reveal that the beta value of capacity building was determined to be 0.787. Consequently, it can be inferred from these results that a 100-percentage increase capacity building is apt to enhance the economic development of women in Mogadishu, Somalia by approximately 78.7 percent. These findings are consistent with the research conducted by Adugna and Heidhuses (2000), as well as Dong, & Featherstone (2010). who emphasized the significance of women capacity building in enhancing the productive capacity of rural households, showing important implications for increasing household income and employment opportunities. Furthermore, Khandker's study (2006) highlighted that capacity building plays a crucial role in reducing poverty, particularly for female, and contributes to overall poverty alleviation at a village level. The results of the study were also consistent with the findings

of Kiriti and Sakwa (2014), who noted that capacity building and skill development promote self-employment capabilities.

Additionally, it emancipates individuals in poverty, including both impoverished individuals and women, from their current circumstances. This allows them to break free from poverty and have control over their own future, becoming instrumental in driving positive change not only for themselves but also for society at large. Khan, (2015) highlighted that capacity building program aimed to enhance the skills of staff in business sector to support them improve their ability, capabilities and effectiveness. Additionally, women empowerment promotes and encourage the participation in entrepreneurship and economic development to create of new jobs. Women entrepreneurs play a crucial role in economic growth by strategically using their businesses to generate stable jobs and invest in economic advancement (Savneet, 2013). Women-owned small businesses are already significantly conducive to the international economy, and their number has increased over time, therefore small medium enterprises have participate creating opportunity employment and economic growth potential. This significant influence to development beyond enterprise growth and increase income (Savneet, 2013). Women's entrepreneurship is key for business and development, despite challenges in establishing and growing businesses. Successful approaches have improved access to finance, training, and markets (Niethammer, 2013).

VI. Conclusion and Recommendation

Capacity building refers to the development of human skills, intellectual capabilities, and talents for a meaningful and satisfied life in societies and communities. This paper attempted to assess the role of capacity building in economic development of women in Mogadishu, Somalia. The study utilized cross sectional research design and employed questionnaire to collect data from 135 research participants. The results indicated that capacity building has a statistically significant positive impact on economic development of women. Based on a Pearson correlation analysis, this result showed a strong positive association between the two variables ($r = 0.787$, $p = 0.05$). The study concluded that implementing capacity building programs could potentially enhance the women's social, and economic capacities, and improve their lives, role and contributions to society. Therefore, the study suggests that institutions and governments should enhance female financial literacy rates by enhancing education quality, removing cultural barriers, and offering training programs in business and managerial skills. The paper also advises is to enhance women's digital literacy by providing training on using technology and digital tools to access markets, promote businesses online, and enhance efficiency.

References:

- [1] Abd Hakim, T., Karia, A. A., David, J., Ginsad, R., Lokman, N., & Zolkafli, S. (2022). Impact of direct and indirect taxes on economic development: A comparison between developed, developing countries. *Cogent Economics & Finance*. .doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2022.2141423
- [2] Ali, A. A., & Mukhongo, A. L. (2016). Factors Influencing on Economic Development of Somalia.
- [3] Al-shami, S. A., Al Mamun, A., Rashid, N., & Al-shami, M. (2021). Microcredit impact on socio-economic development and women empowerment in low-income countries: Evidence from yemen. *Sustainability*, 13(16), 9326. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13169326>.
- [4] Aris, N. M. (2007). SMEs: Building blocks for economic growth. *Department of National Statistics, Malaysia*.
- [5] Ashraf, I., & Ali, A. (2018). Socio-economic well-being and women status in Pakistan: an empirical analysis.
- [6] Bertaux, N., & Crable, E. (2007). Learning about women. Economic development, entrepreneurship and the environment in India: A case study. *Journal of Developmental Entrepreneurship*, 12(04), 467-478.
- [7] Chen, H., & Volpe, R. P. (2002). Gender differences in personal financial literacy among college students. *Financial services review*, 11(3), 289-307.
- [8] Collett, K., & Gale, C. (2009). Training for rural development: Agricultural and enterprise skills for women smallholders. *City and Guilds Centre for Skills Development*, 24-30.
- [9] de Rooij, S. J. G. (2005). Institutional capacity building for rural women's empowerment. *Electronic Journal of Polish Agricultural Universities*, 8(3), np-np.
- [10] Dibie, R., Edoho, F. M., & Dibie, J. (2015). Analysis of capacity building and economic growth in sub-Saharan Africa. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 6(12), 1-25.
- [11] Dong, F., Lu, J., & Featherstone, A. M. (2010). Effects of credit constraints on productivity and rural household income in China.
- [12] Duflo, E. (2012). Women empowerment and economic development. *Journal of Economic literature*, 50(4), 1051-1079.

- [13] Eger, C., Miller, G., & Scarles, C. (2018). Gender and capacity building: A multi-layered study of empowerment. *World Development*, 106, 207-219.
- [14] Ge, T., Abbas, J., Ullah, R., Abbas, A., Sadiq, I., & Zhang, R. (2022). Women's entrepreneurial contribution to family income: innovative technologies promote females' entrepreneurship amid COVID-19 crisis. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 828040.
- [15] Ge, T., Abbas, J., Ullah, R., Abbas, A., Sadiq, I., & Zhang, R. (2022). Women's entrepreneurial contribution to family income: innovative technologies promote females' entrepreneurship amid COVID-19 crisis. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 828040.
- [16] Guled, N. S. (2017). Factors influencing women entrepreneurs' business success in Somalia (Master's thesis, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü).
- [17] Gumbo, B., Forster, L., & Arntzen, J. (2005). Capacity building in water demand management as a key component for attaining millennium development goals. *Physics and Chemistry of the Earth, Parts A/B/C*, 30(11-16), 984-992.
- [18] Handaragama, S., Rathnayake, H., & Uluwaduge, P. (2013). Women's economic participation in rural development. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 1(8), 1-18.
- [19] Heywood, E. (2020). Radio journalism and women's empowerment in Niger. *Journalism Studies*, 21(10), 1344-1362.
- [20] Hjelmström, J. (2017). Feminist perspectives on women empowerment in Tanzania: A case study of why economic development is not enough.
- [21] Hoe, C. H., Isa, F. M., Hin, C. W., Hashim, N., Yunus, J. M., & Abdullah, H. H. (2012). Development of women entrepreneurs: The case of Malaysia. *World*, 2(6), 124-145.
- [22] Humphries, D., Gomez, L., & Hartwig, K. (2011). Sustainability of NGO capacity building in southern Africa: successes and opportunities. *The International journal of health planning and management*, 26(2), e85-e101.
- [23] Ihekwa Hope, C., & Cynthia, E. (2022). WOMEN CAPACITY BUILDING FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA. *IGWEBUIKE: African Journal of Arts and Humanities*, 8(3). DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18277.47848
- [24] Ihekwa Hope, C., & Cynthia, E. (2022). WOMEN CAPACITY BUILDING FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA. *IGWEBUIKE: African Journal of Arts and Humanities*, 8(3). DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18277.47848
- [25] Jabeen, N., & Iqbal, M. Z. (2010). Gender and local governance in Pakistan: Promoting participation through capacity building. *South Asian Studies*, 25(02), 255-281.
- [26] Jahan, F. (2015). Measuring the impact of training for the development of women empowerment in Pakistan. *International Journal of Women Empowerment*, 1(1), 5-12.
- [27] Khan, M. A. (1998). Evaluation capacity building: An overview of current status, issues and options. *Evaluation*, 4(3), 310-328.
- [28] Khan, M. I. (2015). Women empowerment, entrepreneurship, and capacity development. *Journal for Studies in Management and Planning*, 1(9), 43-56. ORCID ID: <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-1116-9448>
- [29] Khan, M. I. (2015). Women empowerment, entrepreneurship, and capacity development. *Journal for Studies in Management and Planning*, 1(9), 43-56.
- [30] Kongolo, M., & Bamgose, O. O. (2002). Participation of rural women in development: A case study of Tsheseng, Thintwa, and Makhalaneng villages, South Africa. *Journal of International Women's Studies*, 4(1), 79-92.
- [31] Mahjabeen R. (2008). Microfinancing in Bangladesh: impact on households, consumption and welfare. *J. Policy Model* 30, 1083-1092. doi: 10.1016/j.jpolmod.2007.12.007 [CrossRef] [Google Scholar] [Ref list]
- [32] Mahmud, A., & Dirawan, G. D. (2016). Effectiveness of Training Model Capacity Building for Entrepreneurship Women Based Empowerment Community. *International Education Studies*, 9(11), 142-150.
- [33] Mehra, R. (1997). Women, empowerment, and economic development. *The Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 554(1), 136-149. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1049571>
- [34] Morrisson, C., & Jütting, J. P. (2004). The impact of social institutions on the economic role of women in developing countries.
- [35] Muthoni, C. S. (2013). Influence of capacity building on financial performance and growth of women owned small and medium enterprises in gikomba market; nairobi county, kenya (Doctoral dissertation, University of Nairobi).
- [36] Niethammer, C. (2013). Women, entrepreneurship and the opportunity to promote development and business. *Brookings blum roundtable policy brief*, 37(1-10).

- [37] Oshikoya, T. W., & Hussain, M. N. (1998). Information technology and the challenge of economic development in Africa. *African development review*, 10(1), 100-133.
- [38] Panth, P. (2021). Economic development: Definition, scope, and measurement. In *No poverty* (pp. 231-243). Cham: Springer International Publishing. doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-69625-6_38-1
- [39] Pollyn, B. S., Barinua, V., & Agi, C. J. (2016). Human capacity building and sustainable development in Nigeria: A value base analysis. *Best International Journal for African Universities*, 3(2), 63-79.
- [40] Rasnayake, S., Handaragama, S., Uluwaduge, P., Susanjika, N., & Kamalrathne, T. (2013). The Role of Informal Women Entrepreneurs in Livelihood Development and Regional Development. *International Journal of Atrs and Commerce*, 2(5), 1-15.
- [41] Razavi S. (2012). World development report 2012: gender equality and development, a commentary. *Dev. Chang*, 43, 423-437. doi: 10.1111/j.1467-7660.2012.01743.x CrossRef [Google ScholarRef list](#).
- [42] Riaz, U., & Chaudhry, M. O. (2021). Role of small and medium enterprises (SME) in women empowerment and poverty alleviation in Punjab, Pakistan. *International Journal of Agricultural Extension*, 9(3), 439-449.
- [43] Sajuyigbe, A. S., & Fadeyibi, I. O. (2017). Women entrepreneurship and sustainable economic development: Evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of Entrepreneurship, Business and Economics*, 5(2), 19-46.
- [44] Saunders, M., Lewis, P., & Thornhill, A. (2009). *Research methods for business students*. Pearson education.
- [45] Savneet, D. (2013). Women entrepreneurship, capacity building and women empowerment. *Int J Hum Soc Sci Invent*, 2(4), 14-17.
- [46] Schlurmann, T., & Siebert, M. (2011). The Capacity Building programmes of GITEWS—visions, goals, lessons learned, and re-iterated needs and demands. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 11(2), 293-300.
- [47] Seyfi, S., Hall, C. M., & Vo-Thanh, T. (2023). The gendered effects of statecraft on women in tourism: Economic sanctions, women's disempowerment and sustainability? In *Gender and Tourism Sustainability* (pp. 285-302). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669582.2020.1850749>
- [48] Shafique, O., & Siddique, N. (2020). The impact of microcredit financing on poverty alleviation and women empowerment: An empirical study on Akhuwat Islamic microfinance. *PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology*, 17(8), 548-562.
- [49] Sharma, A., Dua, S., & Hatwal, V. (2012). Micro enterprise development and rural women entrepreneurship: way for economic empowerment. *Arth Prabhand: A Journal of Economics and Management*, 1(6), 114-127.
- [50] Sohail, M. (2014). Women empowerment and economic development—an exploratory study in Pakistan. *Journal of Business Studies Quarterly*, 5(4), 210.
- [51] Sule Magaji, I. M., & Ahmad, A. I. (2024). Impact Of Small and Medium-Scale Enterprises on Women's Empowerment in Nigeria.
- [52] Tsafack Nanfosso, R. (2011). The state of capacity building in Africa. *World Journal of Science, Technology and Sustainable Development*, 8(2/3), 195-225.
- [53] Usman, A. S. and Tasmin, R. (2016), "The Role of Islamic Micro-finance in Enhancing Human Development in Muslim Countries", *Journal of Islamic Finance*, Vol. 5, No. 1, pp. 053-062. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3233.1762>
- [54] Usman, A. S., & Tasmin, R. (2016). The role of Islamic micro-finance in enhancing human development in Muslim countries. *Journal of Islamic Finance*, 5(1), 053-062. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3233.1762>
- [55] Vincent, C., & Stephen, C. (2015). Local government capacity building and development: Lessons, challenges and opportunities. *Journal of Political Sciences & Public Affairs*, 3(01), 1-5.
- [56] World Health Organization. (2001). What do we know about capacity building?: an overview of existing knowledge and good practice.
- [57] Kulmie, D. A., Hussein, M. S., Abdi, B. M., Abdulle, M. A., Adam, M. A., Bank, P., & Mogadishu, S. (2023). Entrepreneurship training, job creation and youth empowerment. *Asian Social Science*, 19(6), 111. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ass.v19n6p111>